

CIRCULAR SPRINT

7-17 September 2021
 3D printing to foster circular design
 A two-week hybrid design sprint - online and at three fablab locations across Europe

More information and registration:

WWW.CRAFTH.EU

WHAT IS CIRCULAR SPRINT ?

CIRCULAR SPRINT is an intense two-week event where multi-disciplinary teams will solve circular economy challenges with the help of 3D printing. It is an interaction between PhD students, professionals, and companies. The event will be held simultaneously in three different locations in Europe. The goal of the event is to provide new, innovative solutions to the pressing circular economy challenges provided by the local industry partners.

The European [Green Deal](#) has set a goal to reach a completely climate-neutral EU before the year 2050. This pursuit requires bold action, requires us to redefine resource use, and necessitates paradigm shifts in many industry sectors. When it comes to the manufacture of products, additive manufacturing, often referred to as 3D printing, is identified as a potential key technology. It can improve maintenance, recycling, and reparation operations of physical products thus improving their circularity.

LOCATIONS

PREREQUISITES TO APPLY

You are a PhD student or a professional with knowledge in at least one of the following domains:

- 3D Printing
- Materials Science
- Business Modelling
- User Testing
- Market Research
- Circular Economy

PROGRAM

- The first week consists of online lectures via Zoom on circular economy, business modeling, and 3D printing.
- The second week is a hands-on design sprint at the chosen fablab with access to 3D printers, prototyping tools, and software
- Feedback sessions are provided on the way with the company representatives and specialists on circular economy and 3D printing

CIRCULAR SPRINT

A design sprint where circular design and 3D printing meet.

A hands-on course for PhD students and professionals to solve challenging company cases.

- Lecture
- Keynote
- Design Sprint

WEEK 1: Online	Monday 6/9	Tuesday 7/9	Wednesday 8/9	Thursday 9/9	Friday 10/9
9:00		Kick-Off	Morning Booster	Morning Booster	
12:00		Designing a Circular Future	3D Printing for Circularity & Prolonged Product Life	Business Models & 3DP for Circular Economy	
13:00		Meet Your Team & Challenge Introduction	Mapping the Problem	Ideation & Decision	Keynote
17:00					
19:00					
WEEK 2: Fablab	Monday 13/9	Tuesday 14/9	Wednesday 15/9	Thursday 16/9	Friday 17/9
9:00			Morning Booster	Morning Booster	Morning Booster
			Feedback & coaching Lean Startup Validation & Prototyping	Feedback & coaching Prototyping & Testing	Compiling Results & Discussion with the Company
		Cultural Evening Activity			PITCHING
					Jury Moment
19:00					AWARD

* the program may be subject to change.

HOPE TO SEE YOU SOON!

